

THE DEVELOPMENT OF LABUHAN HAJI AS “COASTAL CULINARY TOUR” TO IMPROVE EAST LOMBOK PEOPLE’S ECONOMY IN FACING THE INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION 4.0

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to create new innovations for Labuhan Haji beach into a culinary tourism of destinations. The method which is used in this research is descriptive qualitative, by observation, analysis, surveys and comparison study. Labuhan Haji Beach located on Labuhan Haji district, East Lombok regency, Nusa Tenggara Barat province, Indonesia. In the 1960s, this beach is an International port. The economy of East Lombok centered on this region. However, currently, the existence of this beach looks quite apprehensive. The dock was dead and the environment has been dirty. This makes the economy of the people around the area had been falling off. So, by attention of the local government and young leaders, this beach will have the opportunity as one of the main economic sectors of the people of East Lombok with the base of culinary tourism destinations, with the support of dock, coastline environments, beautiful scenery and internet connection. The culinary which developed and sold is seafood with spices typical of the local area, so as to create a unique flavor. In addition, through this culinary can also establish and introduce the identity of Labuhan Haji area, East Lombok. Then, Labuan Haji new strategy for coastal communities for facing the economic competition in this Industrial Revolution 4.0 era. The result of this research can raise the people’s economic sector in East Lombok by merger the culinary tourism sector, beach, and dock.

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1. Introduction

Today, the use of modern technological tools is undeniable, and has even become a priority for human life. The existence of this technology is essential due to its usefulness for humans in supporting their work and other necessities of life. Various technological inventions, such as cellphones, PCs, computers, followed by the development of internet networks in the form of web access, social media, online payment, and others, have made human life easier. The distance and time that was once a communication barrier between human beings has now been overcome. The development of this technology has become a major benchmark for the development of the 21st century, namely the Industrial Revolution 4.0. The term of Industrial Revolution 4.0 was officially born in Germany, precisely at the Hannover Fair held in 2011 (Kagermann, et al. 2011). The German Chancellor, Angela Merkel (2014) argues that Industry 4.0 is a comprehensive transformation of all industrial production aspects through the incorporation of internet and digital technology with conventional industries. In contrast to previous industrial revolutions, the industrial revolution 4.0 is a new era that have more complexity and wider influence. Technological development that occurs makes it easy for humans in every knowledge field: economy, knowledge, government, and so on. (Mazak, A., & Huemer, C. 2015)Based on Indonesian Pers’ broadcast NO. 53 / HM / KOMINFO / 02/2018, the number of internet users in 2017 in Indonesia has reached 143.26 million people, equivalent to 54.68 percent of the total population of Indonesia. This amount shows an increase of 10.56 million people from the survey results in 2016. This proves that more than half of the population in Indonesia are active internet users.

The above conditions are great opportunity for the use of several sectors in human life, one of which is the economy, since the internet is used to sell various goods. There are many internet-based buying and selling sites today such as OLX.id, e-Bay, Lazada, Tokopedia, etc. Seeing these conditions, it is possible that the internet can also be used as a means of tourism promotion. East Lombok is a district located on Lombok Island, West Nusa Tenggara province. The capital of East Lombok district is Selong. The regency is located on the east coast of Lombok island in the astronomical position 116-117 east longitude and 8-9 south latitude. The land area of East Lombok district is 1,605.55 km² and the sea area is 1,074.33 km² (sipd.kemendagri.go.id). The boundaries of the East Lombok region consist of Central Lombok Regency and North Lombok Regency in the west, the Java Sea in the north, the Alas Strait in the East, and the Indian Ocean in the south. This area has a pretty long coastline since most of the area is bordering the waters. There are 43 that have direct boundaries with the sea which consist of 20 sub-districts. Sambelia is the largest sub-district with an area of 245.22 km². In East Lombok, there is a mountain with the highest peak in East Lombok with an altitude of 3,672 meters above sea level, and is one of the highest mountains in Indonesia. (Geography and Climate. 2016. lomboktimurkab.go.ig)

East Lombok has a large coastline so that this area has a large potential for marine wealth. Therefore, this area has 4 piers namely Kayangan Pier in Labuhan Lombok, Labuhan Haji Pier, Tanjung Luar Pier, and Tanjung Elong Pier in Jerowaru. This makes the sea area one of the main development sectors of East Lombok. There are various marine products that have been developed including seaweed, pearls, groupers, lobsters, and capture fisheries. Fishery products are the result of considerable development. The area of fisheries in East Lombok is 1,074.33 km² with a sustainable fishing potential of 18,242 tons. The utilization of these results is 70% or 752 km², with a production of 3,746 tons. (Enchantment of Pearls from the East: Catalog of Potential East Lombok) East Lombok has many beaches and Gili (small island) which have been developed as tourism site. According to the records of the Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Department of East Lombok Regency, there are 35 Gili in East Lombok waters, including Gili Terawangan, Gili Meno, Gili Air, Gili Bidara, and so on. In addition, there are also beaches that offer beautiful panoramas that attract tourists, such as Pink Beach, Surga Beach, Cemara Beach, Ketapang Beach, and so on. Labuhan Haji Beach is a beach that becomes a pier and is included in the central development sub-unit with a development center in Selong City. Labuhan Haji Beach is located in Labuhan Haji sub-district, East Lombok Regency. This beach was once an international port in the 1960s. The East Lombok community used this port as the starting point for the pilgrimage to Mecca, Saudi Arabia. In addition, this port is also used as the entrance to Chinese trade to the island of Lombok.

The development of coastal tourism in Labuhan Haji is one of the means to improve the standard of living of people around this area. The strategic location as a transit link between Lombok and Sumbawa is an added value for this object to be used as a tourism site. The transit area is an area that is actually not the final destination of a tour, but tourists can enjoy the area for some time, usually the transit area has a strategic location as a link to the other tourist attraction around it (Pitana, 2005: 100). However, at this time the condition of the Labuhan Haji Beach along with its dock is very alarming. The dock that was built in 2007 and completed in 2009 using the regional budget has not yet been operational. Dirty coastal environment, as well as various facilities that are less supportive, made this beach to be abandoned by tourists. For this reason, there is a need for new innovations for the development of the Labuhan Haji beach to be able to restore and revive the economy of the coastal community of Labuhan Haji.

2. Research Method

The method used in this research is descriptive method. Descriptive method is a method used to find elements, characteristics, characteristics of a phenomenon. (Suryana. 2010, *Research Methodology: Practical Model of Quantitative and Qualitative Research*. UPI). Nana Sudjana and Ibrahim (1989: 64) say that descriptive research is a research that seeks to describe a phenomenon, event and event that occurs at the present time where the researcher tries to photograph the events and events that are the center of attention to be described as they are.

Object studies are carried out by observing, surveying visitors, and doing literature study. Field observations or surveys are carried out by visiting the beach at the port of Haji. Observations are carried out by visiting the beach and dock at Haji harbor. This observation was carried out for 1 month.

Literature study is carried out by examining demographic and economic data of the East Lombok community, especially the coastal communities of the Labuhan Haji beach. Literature study is carried out by collecting resources related to research materials, such as data presented by the Central Bureau of Statistics, East Lombok's Office of Fisheries and Maritime Affairs, the Department of Transportation, and so on.

The survey was conducted by collecting data on visitors of Labuhan Haji beach in the last 5 years. The survey was conducted by distributing online forms to the East Lombok community and providing related questions. This survey was attended by 25 people who had lived in East Lombok.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 The Condition of Labuhan Haji Beach

Labuhan Haji beach is located in Labuhan Haji District, East Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara Province. Labuhan Haji subdistrict, which is the location of the Port, is included in the Central Development Area Sub Unit (SSWP) with a development center in the city of Selong. This shows that administratively Labuhan Haji District is included in the Selong urban area. Aside from being a development center in the SSWP, Selong city is also the capital of East Lombok Regency. (Port Master Plan: Labuhan Haji Port, 2009: 14). According to the Central Statistics Agency in East Lombok in Figures 2012, the total population of Labuhan Haji District in 2012 was 53,820 out of a total of 1,123,488 inhabitants in East Lombok Regency.

Based on observations, the condition of Labuhan Haji beach is quite alarming. The coastal environment is very dirty, both in the coastal environment as well as the sea waters. Lots of rubbish piled up and also scattered everywhere. The bad thing is that the garbage is human waste, plastic waste, bottled drinks, instant noodle packaging, and so on. This situation makes Labuhan Haji beach lose its beauty. As a place of open nature, waste produced by humans is the main disturber.

Figure 1. Garbage is scattered on the Labuhan Haji Beach

In addition to garbage, Labuhan Haji beach has dock that also has poor conditions. This dock never operates and looks like a "dead building". This dock was built by the East Lombok regional government using the Regional Budget in 2007 and completed in 2009. However, until now, the dock has not yet been operational. As the result, there are many buildings are in vain, and become objects for people to take a walk and see sunrise. Labuhan Haji's harbor which was at first built in hopes of increasing the quality of life and economy of the community, as the main vector of economy and reviving the glor of Labuhan Haji beach in the end could not be realized. It because the dept of the port has not qualified, the navigation equipment along the port entry has not yet available, and the operational permit still not available.

In line with the construction of the harbor, the government also built a few other facilities such as *berugak* or gazebos and a park. The construction of facilities is accepted to give benefits to the beach environment, as well as the community. The beach's surroundings appear more beautiful and the people can make use of stated facilities. However, these developments are not evenly spread out. Gazebos and the park can only be found on the west side of the dock, not the east.

Figure 2. Gazebos in Labuhan Haji beach

Figure 3. Labuhan Haji harbor gates

3.2 The Labuhan Haji Communities' Economy

The people in the coast of Labuhan Haji are generally employed as merchants and fishermen. The trade sector in the area is generally made up of lower and mid level traders. This can be seen by the shape of stalls and the type of goods. The west side of the dock is filled by small traders with simple stalls held up by bamboo and with fabric roofs. The east side is populated by stall buildings generally built with brick and mortar with a few using bamboo as decorations for cafes and small restaurants as to invoke a natural atmosphere. They sell snacks, and various regional fried foods. The merchants set up shop on the coast. Not only that, the surrounding community also offer various kinds of popular and regionally distinct dishes such as meatball, grilled fish, *lalapan*, *plecing kangkung*, and *nasi kaput*. A few also work as fishermen. The occupation is

done by the husbands. Their catch is processed before being sold on the coast or directly to the market. Their catch contributes to the production of Labuhan Haji illustrated based on Central Bureau of Statistic in *Lombok Timur dalam Angka 2012* in the following table:

Table 1. Fishery production data of each subdistrict in the East Lombok Regency.

NO	Subdistrict	Catch		Cultivation		Total Number	
		Sea	Public Waters	Fish farms	Ponds		Farms
1	Keruak	5.071,00			77,30		5.148,30
2	Jerowaru	790,60		50,50	678,80		1.511,90
3	Sakra				9,70		9,70
4	West Sakra				17,90		17,90
5	East Sakra	162,10		478,20	5,90		646,20
6	Terara				48,85		46,85
7	Montong Gading				491,30	65,80	557,10
8	Sikur				42,50		42,50
9	Masbagik				587,20	11,30	598,50
10	Pringgasele				107,90	217,40	325,30
11	Sukamulia				129,50		129,50
12	Suralaga				48,00	1,00	49,00
13	Selong				167,40		167,40
14	Labuhan Haji	248,30			8,30		256,60
15	Pringgabaya	5.948,60			3,10		5.951,70
16	Suela				0,75		0,75
17	Aikmel				556,70	49,50	606,20
18	Wanasaba				50,20	2,40	52,60
19	Semalun				0,80		0,80
20	Sambelia	299,70		2.260,20	0,60		2.560,50
		12.520,30	00,00	2.788,90	3.022,70	347,40	18.679,30

Based on the data above, the fishery sector results of Labuhan Haji beach can still be considered lower than in other subdistricts. If the production results above are ranked, Labuhan Haji district would be ranked 10th of the 20 subdistricts in the Lombok Timur Regency. This position, indicated to have a still unstable and rather low economic condition, can be seen from the catch and fish cultivation results that have too much distance. This proves that the people of Labuhan Haji are still in a low economic condition because of their inability to maximize the existing sea potential. The fusion of the trade sector covers up the inadequacy of catch of the fishermen by the people of the Labuhan Haji beach, but the trade sector has not helped enough in advancing the economy of the people of the coast because it's still considered a low trade sector.

3.3 Visitors of Labuhan Haji Beach

Nowadays, Lombok has started to be known by the wider society, whether that be locals, or foreigners. The beauty of the island of Lombok has been much exposed and can rival the beauty of the island of Bali. Lombok has started to be visited a lot by tourists, both local and international. The situation has made Lombok noticed by the international world. In the year 2016, it was hailed with the *World Halal Tourism Award*. The honor was a repetition of the previous award as the *World's Best Halal Honeymoon Destination* in *The World Halal Travel Summit and Exhibition*.

The construction of facilities alongside reparations in various tourism sectors have been done by the regional government and people. In a few beaches, such as in the Senggigi beach in West Lombok, there can be found many hotels, cafés, restaurants, recreation, and other facilities that support tourism in Senggigi beach, succeeding in attracting local and international tourists. Mandalika beach in Central Lombok also have made much threading and construction, such as building hotels, resorts and mosques which are implementations of Lombok's *World Halal Tourism Award*. The construction of the tourism sectors in Lombok are based on three main things. Gamal Suwanto (1997: 19) states that efforts of objects and attractiveness of sites are categorized into three groups: efforts of objects and attractiveness of natural sites, of cultural sites, and of special interest sites. The melding of nature and culture becomes the pivot that can elevate uniqueness in the tourism sector. For example, Mandalika beach combines the beauty of nature and the culture of the Lombok people. Every year, the *Bau Nyale* festival, alongside the cultural performance of *Presean*, is held at the beach.

However, unlike the advancements and achievements of Lombok, Labuhan Haji beach is becoming ever quieter. This beach has started to be left by tourists. The people's economy sector is weakening, and various development in the coast is futile. This is in spite of Labuhan Haji having natural wonders which are particularly beautiful in the morning. The beauty of the sunrise is an attractive view. Aside from that, the beach has brownish, rounded sand with waves that aren't too small (Dishubkominfo, 2010: 2). The lack of development based on tourist attractions like those stated by Gamal Suwanto above is one of the reasons of the fading existence of Labuhan Haji beach. This beach only offers sunrise panorama that's not balanced by tourism development in other areas such as culture or special interests that could increase its attractiveness. A few other reasons as to why Labuhan Haji beach is less desired are the unclean environment and the organization of the surroundings as well as bad facilities. Based on survey results, the following are responses of visitors of the beach.

Figure 1. Visitor response

The survey above was done by 25 respondents. As much as 15 or 60% of them stated that the beach was dirty, 4 or 16% responded that the beach was good, 3 or 12% expressed that the facilities were improving, and another 3 or 12% said that the beach's organization or layout was poor. Thus, it can be concluded that more than half of the respondents said that Labuhan Haji beach was still unclean. Looking at those problems, Labuhan Haji beach is expected to do various corrections and development around the beach. There needs to be new innovation to be able to elevate the presence of Labuhan Haji beach as well as helping the economy of the coastal community, especially with the competitiveness of tourism in Lombok. By taking advantage of

the existing commerce section on the coast, as well as fishery production acquired by Labuhan Haji fishermen, there exists a major opportunity for the formation of a culinary tourism sector in the area. The processing of fishery products can become unique and distinct dishes that can become an excellent product that can be further developed. In addition, combining the result of fishing and other distinct Lombok cuisine can be made as a main asset for the development of the culinary tourism sector going forward.

3.4 Promotional Media for Labuhan Haji Beach

Going into the age of the industrial revolution 4.0, the use of the internet becomes the main and most important focus in people's lives to find various information on many things, including tourist destinations. A large part of this still depends on the usage of Google and other search engines, as well as electronic news outlets. Innovation in the development of a culinary tourism sector in labuhan Haji beach requires promotional media. The development of a fast website can open promotional possibilities on the web. However, it can be less effective considering not all people know about labuhan Haji beach that would then allow them to search information on it on the web. Because of this, social media as a part of the industrial revolution 4.0 that has been quickly adopted by society and various groups is an effective promotional media. The type of social media that would be effective would be Instagram. This photo based social media would be able to display photos of the beauty of Labuhan Haji beach, as well as those of existing culinary centers. The use of the *Sponsor* feature on this platform would also allow for the increase in viewers to the posts that will be relied upon by the account and increase visits to the instagram account, thus increasing the number of visitors interested in coming and purchasing culinary products that exist there. The advantage of Instagram's features as well as the beauty of Labuhan Haji beach matches perfectly. The usage of media that's popular and used by many people is apt to become a solution in increasing the economy in the area of culinary tourism based on technology to face the industrial revolution 4.0.

4. Conclusion

Considering the data and the existing potential in Labuhan Haji beach as in the discussion above, the development of labuhan Haji beach is heavily required. The existence of unoptimal functioning harbors pushes the need for other innovation that is required to increase the presence and economy of the local community on the coast of Labuhan Haji. The development of tourism suggested in the beach is insufficiently effective considering the existing conditions. Culinary tourism can become a new innovation that is perfect to be developed in Labuhan Haji beach. The existence of various cafes and restaurants that provide seafood and a few local dishes need to be further increased in the whole of the whole of the Lombok coast. Environmental concerns such as the lack of cleanliness and other supporting facilities require the advent of partnerships and full attention by the regional government and related government agencies. The implementation of programs concerning the development of the beach has to focus on the interest of the community in order to reach higher levels of welfare should be the government's duty. Aid to elevate the economy of the people with various developments and its main program should become a priority of the government to reach good public welfare, especially those of the coastal community. The industrial revolution 4.0 demands that all forms of development to a program is based on technology to ease its implementation. For that reason, the usage of social media as promotional media for the development of the culinary tourism sector in Labuhan Haji in the form of a social media account on the Instagram platform would be very effective. It is hoped that with the advent of the development of a culinary tourism sector and technologically based promotion, the existence and economy of the coastal community of Labuhan Haji beach can be repaired.

Reference

- [1] Badan Pusat Statistik Kabupaten Lombok Timur. 2012. *Lombok Timur dalam Angka 2012*. Selong.
- [2] Bahri, et al. 2010. *Kegeneman Suku Sasak*. Mataram: Penerbit Pustaka Widya.
- [3] Dishubkominfo Kabupaten Lombok Timur. *Rencana Induk Pelabuhan Labuhan Haji 2009*. Sipd.kemendagri.go.id. Accessed on 27 Juli 2018, on 16.23 WITA.
- [4] Geografi dan Iklim. 2016. *Lomboktimurkab.go.ig*. Accessed on August 10, 2018 on 15.35 WIB.
- [5] Kagermann, et al. 2011. *Industrie 4.0: Mit dem Internet der Dinge auf dem Weg zur 4. industriellen Revolution*. <http://www.vdi-nachrichten.com/Technik-Gesellschaft/Industrie-40-Mit-Internet-Dinge-Weg-4-industriellen-Revolution>, Accessed on June 17, 2017.
- [6] Mazak, A., & Huemer, C. 2015. *A Standards Framework for Value Networks in the Context of Industry 4.0*. In *Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management (IEEM)*. 2015 IEEE International Conference, Hongkong.
- [7] Public Relation and Protocol of East of Lombok Regency. *Pesona Mutiara dari Timur: Katalog Potensi Lombok Timur*.
- [8] Indonesian Pers' broadcast No. 53/HM/KOMINFO/02/2018 date Februari 19, 2018 about "Jumlah Pengguna Internet 2017 Meningkat, Kominfo akan Terus Lakukan Percepatan Pembangunan Broadband". (https://kominfo.go.id/content/detail/12640/siaran-pers-no-53hmkominfo022018-tentang-jumlah-pengguna-internet-2017-meningkat-kominfo-terus-lakukan-percepatan-pembangunan-broadband/0/siaran_pers). Accessed on August 10, 2018 on 16.00 WIB.
- [9] Setyo, Sigit. 2016. *Pariwisata NTB Sabet Tiga Penghargaan Internasional*. <http://radarlombok.co.id/pariwisata-ntb-sabet-tiga-penghargaan-internasional.html>. accessed on Agustus 9, 2018 on 14.09 WIB.
- [10] Sudjana, Nana and Ibrahim. 1989. *Penelitian dan Penilaian Pendidikan*. Bandung: Sinar Baru.
- [11] Suryana. 2010. *Metodologi Penelitian: Model Praktis Penelitian Kuantitatif dan Kualitatif*. Bandung: Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia.